

KEY INDICATORS

Being a small country, with 66 hectares, Malta had the tiniest area under organic management, constituting 0.6% of the country's farmland. Malta was thus the country with the smallest organic area share and the only county with less than 1% of its farmland under organic management. Retail sales data is not available for Malta.

ORGANIC FARMLAND

2001

2022

Area* (Share of Total Farmland)

N/D

66 ha (0.6%)

Area Growth from 2001 to 2022

N/D

ORGANIC LAND USE & AQUACULTURE

2001

2022

Arable Land* (Share of Total)

N/D

41 ha (0.5%)

Permanent Crops* (Share of Total)

N/D

24 ha (1.7%)

Grassland* (Share of Total)

N/D

N/D

Aquaculture Production (Share of Total)

N/D

N/D

ORGANIC OPERATORS

2001

2022

Producers (Share of Total)

N/D

25 (0.33%)

Aquaculture Producers

N/D

N/D

Processors

N/D

7

Importers

N/D

34

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES

2001

2022

Retail Sales (Share of Total)

N/D

N/D

Per Capita Consumption

N/D

N/D

Retail Sales Growth from 2001 to 2022

N/D

Imports

N/D

86 t

Source: FiBL survey based on national data sources, Eurostat and TRACES/European Commission in the framework of the OrganicTargets4EU project

*In conversion and fully organic

KEY INDICATORS

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC FARMLAND IN MALTA

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey based on Eurostat Nic Lampkin

CAP ORGANIC POLICY SUPPORT

The Malta CAP strategic plan provides for a very large increase in supported organic area, expenditure and payment rates compared with 2018. This is in part a reflection of the horticultural focus and small farm size of Maltese agriculture, with only 500 ha being targeted for organic support, but it also represents a desire to incentivise conversion so as to kick-start the organic sector, which is currently very small.

CONVERSION & MAINTENANCE

2018

2027

Land Area Supported (Change from 2018)*	10 kha	260 kha (+4,075%)
Share of Total Agricultural Area Supported*	0.1 %	2.5% (+4,000%)
Share of Certified Organic Area Supported (Change)*	13%	-
Expenditure per Year*	0.002 M€	103 M€ (+43,539%)
Expenditure per Hectare Supported*	374 €	3,913 € (+945%)

SHARE OF CAP RESOURCES

CAP EXP. 2023-2027 ORGANIC SHARE*

Organic Farming Support (P2)*	2 M€	100%
Eco-Schemes (P1)	9 M€	13.2%
Agri-Environment, Climate, Welfare (P2)	8 M€	
Total CAP Expenditure	160 M€	1.4%

*including in-conversion and fully organic land

CAP ORGANIC CONVERSION AND MAINTENANCE PAYMENTS FOR DIFFERENT LAND USES

INDICATOR	YEAR	FUND	GRASSLAND	ARABLE CROPS	HORTICULTURE	FRUIT CROPS	GRAPES	OLIVES
Conversion Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	1209	1209	1209	1209	1209	1209
	2023	P2	4378	4378	4378	4378	4378	4378
Change from 2019 to 2023			262%	262%	262%	262%	262%	262%
Maintenance Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	555	555	555	555	555	555
	2023	P2	3614	3614	3614	3614	3614	3614
Change from 2019 to 2023			550%	550%	550%	550%	550%	550%
Conversion Support Higher than Maintenance	2019		118%	118%	118%	118%	118%	118%
	2023		21%	21%	21%	21%	21%	21%

P1 (Pillar 1) European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF); P2 (Pillar 2) European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and national co-financing

NATIONAL ORGANIC ACTION PLAN

Malta is at very early stage of the development of its organic sector and its first action plan reflects the need to establish new initiatives in a number of areas, appropriate to the current and planned scale of the sector.

TARGETS

	PERIOD	LAND AREA TARGET	OTHER TARGETS
Previous Action Plan	None	None	None
Current Action Plan	2023-30	5% of UAA by 2030	None

KEY ACTIONS

PREVIOUS ACTION PLAN (NONE)

No Previous Plan

PRODUCTION

Substantially increased support payments, also for organic aquaculture and other investments

No Previous Plan

MARKETS

Producer organisations support; development of direct sales, farmers markets and hospitality catering; facilitate access to plant protection products not currently registered in Malta

No Previous Plan

INFORMATION

Promotion campaigns including bio-districts and bio-trails; provide advisory and mentoring services, training and research; market data collection and reporting

CURRENT ACTION PLAN (2023-2030)

AQUACULTURE

The organic share of total aquaculture production in Malta is negligible. Malta was not included in our analysis of the EMFF (2014-2020) and EMFAF (2021-2027) operational programmes and the Multi-annual National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture, but financial support for organic aquaculture production and certification, and consumer information, is referred to in the current action plan from 2023. As the funding is project specific and there is no ring-fenced organic budget, statistics on organic aquaculture support expenditure are not available.